

Necessity-centred education: building bridges between society and learning in the future

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Abstract

The principle of regenerative agriculture is to focus on the soil and nurture it with microorganisms, minerals and organic matter, so that plants can grow healthy and the land can recover from desertification. In a similar way, regenerative technologies and regenerative economies nurture the human emotions with empathy, generosity, sharing and solidarity, so that human relationships can grow healthy and society can develop towards peace, equality and prosperity for all, in a balanced relationship with nature. Yet, the current situation is not optimistic: wars, genocides, hunger, extreme poverty, climatic disasters, loss of biodiversity, behavioural diseases, forced migrations, racism, gender violence and so on provide a series of challenges for humankind. Western civilization is reaching its own limits and it is facing the consequences of sustained exponential growth. Greed and power are the driving forces of the world. Each civilization has educated its youngsters to the needs of its means of living. Societies of hunter-gatherers train their children to learn what plants are edible. Craftsmen have apprentices that learn their craft. Our current civilization educates engineers and economists to develop the enterprises and technologies that serve the purposes of the rich and the powerful. The time has come to create the foundations of the next civilization, that centres the education on the global needs of humankind, and the true necessities of the people and the environment. Our current education system is organised from disciplines to applications. Yet, the education system we promote should be centred on meaningful challenges, and find all available means to solve them. Empathy, generosity, solidarity, cooperation, and sharing are the values that should replace our current profit-based behaviour. Thus, maybe the time has come to transform our concept of an engineer from someone who is able to devise new technologies, to someone who is able to solve problems even without technologies, if none are required. This paper is intended as a side documentation for a workshop. Our goal, then, is not to provide solutions, but to set up provoking questions and situations, hoping for a fruitful discussion.

Keywords: The risks of technology; Exponential Growth; Global challenges; Human-scale necessities; Regenerative Technologies; Necessity-Centred Education.

The shortest path from barbarism to decadence is civilization
From the film *L'aventure c'est l'aventure*

Life does not have a meaning. The meaning is life
Mata Amritanandamayi

La vie est belle, le monde est pourri
Manu Chao

1 Introduction

Every society educates their young people to be prepared for those activities that the society requires for its proper development. Thus, hunter-gatherer societies teach the youngsters to know which plants are edible and which are not, and how to hunt. And craftsmen have apprentices to carry out and learn their craft.

Our current society has reached a high level of complexity and the young people have a wide range of activities to choose from, ranging from the agricultural sector, to industry, services and cultural activities. Yet society is organised around the marketplace, and science, technology and economics play a central role in the development of the economy. Power and money rule the world.

In the last 200 years, our civilization is undergoing an unprecedented expansion that reaches all aspects of life. Population growth, continued growth of world GDP, economic inequality, technological innovation, exploitation and depletion of natural resources, exploitation of data and information, urbanisation in ever larger cities, pollution, environmental degradation, and so on.

As engineers we know that unlimited exponential growth is unfeasible, yet the economic system requires sustained growth. In spite of all warnings (Club de Roma, 1972), our society is not able to slow down, and there are clear symptoms that we are reaching the limits of the planet (Meadows et al, 2004; Dixon-Declève et al. 2022).

Sadly, our society has yet proven unable to solve the above issues, together with the issues of coexistence among fellow individuals and with the rest of nature. Wars, genocides, racism, gender violence, inequality, poverty, starvation, migrations, climate change, loss of biodiversity, desertisation, and so on fill the pages of our newspapers every day.

The economy is centred in consumerism and profit making, rather than focusing on the needs of the people and the environment. The activities of society are ever more complex, and only a few of them are related to subsistence tasks.

This paper focuses on the causes of the current crises, the challenges that must be faced, and the approach that must be taken for a new civilization to emerge. And therefore, we focus on what education should be *in the future* to reach peace, equality and prosperity for all.

This paper has been written from the stand-point of pacifism, and sustainability: we claim that a resource or a consumption habit is *sustainable* if it is not harmful to oneself, the others or the environment, and it is available to all, now and for the next 7 generations.

In section 2 we focus on the role of technology in the current crises, and section 3 points out how money is the main cause and the tool for inequality and exponential growth. Section 4 is a sample of the challenges of our civilization and section 5 is a description of human scale necessities, as opposed to consumerism. Section 6 proposes the use of natural economies and regenerative technologies for subsistence and satisfaction of the human needs. And section 7 suggests some ideas on what education in this utopian future would be.

This paper is intended as documentation for a workshop. Participants to the workshop will be organised in teams, and each team will receive a deck of cards with 6 suits. Each suit corresponds to one of the mentioned subjects:

- The power and risks of technology (section 2).
- Money and economic growth (section 3).
- Challenges of our society (section 4).
- Human scale necessities (section 5).
- Natural economy and regenerative technologies (section 6).
- Human scale, necessity-centred education in the future (section 7).

For each suit, each card contains a brief question or statement related to the corresponding subject. Each team will choose 5 cards from each suit, and will prepare a poster with their reflection on how education should be in the future. The workshop will then proceed with a short presentation of the posters and a general discussion.

Rather than expanding each subject, which would take a lot of writing space, the rest of this paper is an inventory of the questions and statements that will be found on the cards during the workshop.

Of course, the goal of this paper is not to provide solutions, which we do not pretend to have, but to think out of the box and foster reflection and discussion. Hopefully, the workshop will elicit potential paths of regeneration.

2 The Power and Risks of Technology

This section poses the question of the risks of technology. It might even be that technology in itself, as a human activity, is the risk. Maybe there is no way to prevent the unexpected consequences of technology, its transformation power, the leap in productivity, its misuses and its spread. In an ever faster pace, technology has transformed the planet into its current predicament,

Not to mention the crucial role of technology in warfare.

- What happened to the Tuareg culture when they first saw the 4-wheel-drives of the Paris-Dakar Rally?
- Imagine that you have just invented The Drone. How can you prevent its use for surveillance or warfaring purposes?
- People say that the tools are neutral, that the *use* of the tool is what is under question. But what is the neutrality of a war missile?
- Inventions have multiple applications. Some are good and some are not. But you can be confident that, if malicious applications are possible, somebody will put them into use.
- Technology is an amplifier. The capacity of harm of a hammer is much less than that of an atomic bomb.
- The technology of today makes the magic of the past become true (and the dreams of science fiction writers). Beware what you dream of.
- What is at stake if a nuclear plant leaks? Why should we take the risk?
- Once you try them, it is practically impossible to renounce the commodities of technology.
- Who could expect that fertilisers and pesticides would poison the aquifers?
- A substantial part of technology is of military origin, or funded by the "defence" departments. Companies, afterwards, take advantage of the research.
- Of all possible technological developments, only those that make profit thrive.
- Most technologies are out of reach for the majority and, therefore, they are not sustainable.
- Many technologies overexploit and deplete the resources they use.
- The word *progress* is a tricky word, because it is supposed to be "good". But it often hides unexpected consequences (Wessels, 2023).
- If you never left your city, you don't know what the stars look like. Or where the milk comes from.
- Technology-based productivity increases exponentially. Those who start later will become dependent and will never catch up.
- Our current education and research system is centred around disciplines and crafts. New devices are first invented and then marketised, even if they are not necessary.
- Thanks to technology, the standard of living has risen... for a third of the world population.

3 Money and Economic Growth

The goal of our economy is sustained exponential growth (percentual growth of GDP). Moreover, the growth of the economy is actually a *requirement* for the economic system to survive. Yet, resources are limited and, therefore, exponential growth is not sustainable.

Money, the wealth concentration tool, is the technology that makes this economic system possible.

The western society (in a broad sense) is facing an unprecedented crisis.

- Money is the technology of trade (Ferguson, 2009; Wild L, 2011).

- Money is an intermediary between human activity and consumption. Rather than producing what we need, we work for money and buy the goods we use.
- Our economic system fosters inequality (Piketty, 2015)
- The values of patriarchy are power and money.
- Money and trade foster individualism and selfishness.
- Those with no income starve. Those with a low income hardly survive. Those with a medium income, consume commodities. Those with a large income save and buy luxury assets... Those with obscene amounts of income rule the world.
- Publicity promises what the majority cannot attain.
- Banks provide... at an interest rate. Or they keep the collateral.
- The rewards of capital are exponential (percentage). The rewards of labour are linear. Resources are not rewarded, but exploited.
- The benefits of trade are larger for the party with absolute advantage, and trade perpetuates the inequality. Ricardo's model legitimates the exploitation of the poor. Let Tom Bradley mown its own grass!
- Market equilibrium is the mechanism by which to tell those who can afford a product from those who cannot. Those with a larger budget get the bigger surplus.
- Picture a simple economic model with families on one side and companies on the other. Families buy food and sell labour. Companies buy labour and sell food. If companies make a profit, what happens to the families?
- Micro-credits monetize otherwise self-sufficient subsistence economies. They at the base of an ever growing pyramidal scam.
- Adam Smith said that, even if the parties in the market look for the maximisation of their profit, society as a whole is better off. Is this not a paradox?
- Big companies earn big profits by cheating very little from a lot of customers. A thousand slightly unfair trades is a big scam.
- Loaning is an explicit form of usury.
- Most of the money in circulation is created by the banks by lending money. At the end of the day, when the loan is paid back, banks still reclaim an interest. But the money for those interests was never created (Duran, 2009).
- Banks make loans today in order to create money for the reimbursement of yesterday's interest (exponential growth).
- If all companies are expected to make profit, where does the money come from?
- The main misuse of money is called speculation.
- Money is not at reach for everyone. Therefore, money is *not* a sustainable good.
- Money makes money, only if money is scarce.
- Inequality grows both during economic expansions and during economic recessions.
- Since banks decide who they lend money to, they have the power to determine which projects can be carried out and which cannot.
- The financial system is a pyramidal scam.
- Who has the money sets the price. The marketplace is dominated by monopolies and monopsonies.
- The market cannot deal with unemployment, even when there remain a lot of things to do.
- Poorly paid labour is today's slavery.
- Investors are said to put their wealth at risk. But what is the legitimacy of their wealth, in the first place?
- The price of goods does not depend on their intrinsic value, or the necessities they satisfy. The price is set to maximise profit.
- The marketplace favours individualism, egotism, and massive consumption.
- There are goods and commodities fit for every income level: 1, 10, 100, 1000, 10.000 ... 1.000.000.000. Marketing offers each of us commodities for the next level, leading to frustration or indebtment.
- Leisure is a commodity.
- Migration is the consequence of economic inequalities.
- The current economic model relies on the assumption of unlimited growth, which is not sustainable.

- Economic growth is a *requirement* for the economic system to prevail.
- Money is a zero sum system. If someone takes a profit, someone else must take a loss.
- If every business is supposed to make profit, then there need to be more businesses to generate the money (exponential growth).
- Money is a cultural abstraction. And a harmful one.
- Debt is a slavery system (Graeber, 2012).
- The main role of the state is to protect the right of property. But property is concentrated in the hands of a few.
- In the beginning there was the land and the people. Then, a few of them claimed ownership over it.

4 Challenges of our Society

Our society has reached the limits of the planet in its exploitation of resources, and half its population is currently living in poverty. Genderism, ageism, racism and other isms are present everywhere. Nature is being polluted and depleted. Many species are disappearing, War and violence are commonplace.

The future of humankind depends on our ability to solve these challenges.

- What technologies are required to achieve peace?
- Suggest three different ways to prevent the accumulation of wealth.
- Genocides are a recurrent situation in history.
- Our civilization is undergoing an explosion, and reaching the limits (Thuillier, 1995; Sempere, 2023)
- More than half the world population lives in poverty.
- In our society, our lifestyle is stressful and leads to mental diseases.
- Everyone should have access to common resources such as unpolluted air, water, food, accommodation, etc.
- Population is overconcentrated in big cities.
- Most of us live alienated from nature.
- Many countries, formerly exploited, are currently burdened by public debt (Auditoria Ciudadana, 2013).
- An unprecedented amount of species are under the risk of extinction.
- Many regions live in misery as a result of western colonisation and exploitation.
- People in poor regions have no other alternative than migration.
- Migrants are refused their right to live at home (misery), and elsewhere (racism).
- Big cities are full of homeless people.
- The values of care taking and reproduction are underestimated.
- We live under all sorts of violence, especially gender violence.
- The leftovers of our industrial society are causing climate change, with the risk of major climate disasters.
- Heavy fertilisation and pesticides are causing desertification of the land.
- Monoculture and the hijacking of seeds prevent traditional subsistence agriculture (Shiva, 1999).
- Deforestation harms the lungs of the planet.
- We live in a world of selfishness and individualistic relationships.
- All species deserve respect.
- Natural resources are being depleted because of the consumption habits of the wealthy.
- The western ways of living produce pollution in land, sea and air. Even the stratosphere is full of satellite garbage.
- Films and media promote violence.
- Our economic system has no solutions for unemployment, even when there is work to be done.
- Many occupations are unproductive and frustrating.

5 Human-scale Necessities

This section is based primarily on the work of Max-Neef (1986), that distinguishes between necessities, satisfiers and goods.

According to Max-Neef, human necessities are subsistence, protection, affection, understanding, participation, recreation, creation, identity, freedom and transcendence. Satisfiers are the means by which necessities are realised, and goods are their practical counterpart (artefacts, technologies and services).

- Accommodation is a satisfier for the need of subsistence. There exist many kinds of accommodation. There is no need for luxury (other than ostentation).
- You can realise your need for recreation by singing a song or buying a yacht. One of them does not require money.
- Poverty is not really the lack of money, but the inability to satisfy some of the needs.
- Breastfeeding is a synergetic satisfier. It realises several needs: survival, affection, protection, identity etc, in both the mother and the child.
- Drinking is a satisfier for the need of subsistence: many commercial drinks, rather than satisfy the thirst, actually harm the health of the drinker.
- The term necessity is usually understood as the lack of something. But most human-scale necessities are actually potentiated when they are satisfied.
- The ecological farmer Fukuoka said that he never worked. He just wandered around his garden and did what he saw that was necessary (Korn, 2017).
- When artefacts become an end in themselves, consumers become dependent on them.
- The sense of belonging to a group is a satisfier of the necessities of participation and identity.
- Associations and neighbourhoods satisfy the necessity of participation, and enhance protection, affection, identity and freedom.
- Mindful meditation is a satisfier for the need of transcendence.
- Books are artefacts that can satisfy the needs of understanding and leisure.
- Autonomy and self-esteem satisfy the need for liberty.
- All necessities are equally important for human-scale development.
- Bioconstruction is a realisation of sustainable accommodation.
- Music, arts and theatre satisfy the needs of understanding, creation and participation.

6 Natural Economy and Regenerative Technologies

The principle of regenerative agriculture is to focus on the soil and nurture it with microorganisms, minerals and organic matter, so that plants can grow healthy and the land can recover from desertification. Apart from capturing water in the soil, like a sponge.

In a similar way, regenerative technologies and regenerative economies (Col-lectiu Mostassa, 2017) nurture the human emotions with empathy, generosity, sharing and solidarity, so that human relationships can grow healthy and society can develop towards peace, equality and prosperity for all, in a balanced relationship with nature.

- Reclaim the commons! (Subirats, 2016; Tirole, 2016; Shiva, 2020)
- The alternative to money is not bartering, but sharing.
- Sharing promotes emotions of altruism, solidarity, generosity, belonging and socialising.
- Degrowth is a must (Kallis, 2018).
- You can be poor in terms of money, but still you can be prosperous if you can realise your necessities (Shiva, 1988).
- Downshifting is not having less, but making a better use of what you have (Linz et al, 2007)
- In a world with no trade there is room for creativity.

- In a world with no money many occupations would become unnecessary. Imagine the amount of free workforce.
- Non-commercial satisfaction of our necessities is a means of self-fulfilment.
- Care taking should prevail over patriarchy values.
- Good habits regenerate health.
- If we focus on our necessities, we will find the proper and simplest solutions.
- The realisation of most necessities does not require “hard” technologies.
- Growing local gardens would prevent starvation when the crisis of the economic system arrives. Growing gardens for survival would accelerate the fall of the economic system. Win-win. Let’s sow tomatoes!
- Seed balls is a technique for preventing desertisation (Fukuoka, 2009; Fukuoka, 2013).
- Regenerative agriculture focuses on nurturing the soil (Schreefel et al, 2020; Wikipedia).
- Regenerative agriculture does not require big machinery.
- Sharing and regenerative technologies nurture the human soul.
- A new civilization can grow if we are able to de-westernise our societies.
- A requirement for a technology to be regenerative is that it has no potential misuses.
- Bioconstruction refers to the use of environmentally friendly materials and techniques in building and architecture.
- Regenerative technologies do not pollute the environment, but they regenerate it.
- It is better to prevent the causes than to mend the consequences.
- Polluting less is still polluting. We need cleansing solutions.
- Culture does not need to be a market commodity. The arts are a satisfier for the need of creation.
- Small communities provide face-to-face communication and require less infrastructure.
- Regenerative technologies seek solutions both in traditional knowledge and in creativity.
- Rather than inventing and selling new commodities, engineering should focus on the simplest solutions to human-scale necessities.
- In a necessity-centred society, many disciplines will no longer be required. Imagine the amount of workforce that would be liberated.
- It is hard to think that our western civilization will be able to solve the challenges it has created. The hope is on indigenous, money free societies (Martinez-Alier, 2011; Tirole, 2018).
- When the collapse arrives (and it is not far away) only those with locally subsistence resources will thrive.
- Regenerative economy uses money just once. It uses money in the beginning to provide for the tools and external materials, then it continually produces food, thanks to the land that provides for free.
- Regenerative economy transforms money for food, from the bottom of the pyramid to the top.
- Regenerative economy is based on sharing, rather than money transactions or bartering.
- In regenerative accounting, rather than a number in a sheet (the balance of money in their account), each person will take note of their necessities, an explanation of the things that they have done or given to others, and an explanation of the favours and goods they have received. Those accounts should be qualitative, avoiding quantification.

7 Human-scale, necessity-centred, education in the future

Each civilization has educated its youngsters to the needs of its means of living. Societies of hunter-gatherers train their children to learn what plants are edible. Craftsmen have apprentices that learn their craft. Our current civilization educates engineers and economists to develop weapons, or ever new commodities to furnish the military and the marketplace, enriching a few.

The time has come to create the foundations of the next civilization, that centres the education on the global needs of humankind, and the true necessities of the people and the environment. Thus, maybe the time has come to transform our concept of an engineer from someone who is able to devise new technologies, to someone who is able to solve problems even without technologies, if none are required.

If we have to build bridges between society and learning in the future, we must rethink our whole education system.

In such an utopian society:

- Future engineers would know what is at stake.
- Education and research would be organised around necessities and challenges, in order to provide sustainable solutions.
- Every young person would have to learn and practice subsistence crafts.
- Young people would have to learn how to grow food and, eventually, raise cattle in a regenerative way.
- Young people would learn the procedures of regenerative economies, and regenerative accounting.
- Engineering would be the ability to creatively solve problems (wit) using a wide range of knowledge and skills.
- Learning traditional crafts would be necessary for necessities such as clothing or building furniture.
- From the need to the solution, rather than from the invention to its economically feasible application.
- Education would be student-centred, with the students developing their own learning path.
- Children and youngsters would learn the satisfactors for their human-scale needs.
- Children and young people would be grown with the values of empathy, solidarity and love.
- Children should be able to freely develop their natural potential (Wild R, 2002).
- Schools and learning institutions, when necessary, would use practical workshops rather than frontal lectures.
- Education would incorporate aspects such as emotional intelligence, interpersonal skills, creativity, critical thinking, and self-awareness.
- Children and young people would learn the habits of a healthy means of living.
- Education in health would prevent diseases.
- A healthy sex education would prevent many misbehaviours.
- Education would value collaboration, empathy, and respect, fostering a sense of belonging and community among students and educators alike.
- Educators would be facilitators of the apprentice's learning process.
- Young people would learn by actually carrying out the necessary activities for their fulfilment.

8 Recapitulation

This paper focused on the education of the *next* civilization. Our current western society, ruled by the greed for money and power, has proved incapable of solving the challenges and problems that the exploitation of people and resources has generated. Technology has changed the world in unexpected and unsustainable ways. Money has become a wealth concentration machine, and the natural needs of human beings have been coopted by technologies and artefacts that alienate us from ourselves and the environment, and contribute to inequality and frustration. Wars, starvation, climate change.. these are the actual challenges that need to be urgently addressed by means of regenerative and sustainable technologies.

In this utopian future, education would be centred in the realisation of human-scale necessities.

You may say that I am a dreamer, but I am not the only one
John Lennon, *Imagine*

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